

Muons Lifetime Stored in a Circular Ring

Didier François Viel

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email : arcopodias@gmail.com

1 Abstract

« E pur si muove ! »

Galileo

In Galileo time, to contradict church sciences was liable to imprisonment or death. Nowadays, you are being ostracized by academic science, but it is like dying for those who desires to pursue a career in the scientific world. In this paper, our contradiction is not on the fact that muons circulating in a circular ring don't have their lifetime enhanced, but it is about the reason why it is so, on the basis of substantiated physical phenomena.

The muons enhanced lifetime has been shown in a series of experiments on a quantum parameter, in which an anomaly was detected, called the "muon (g-2) anomaly". To get a better precision on the "muon (g-2) anomaly", the experiment was done on muons stored in a circular ring. When it was evident, from these experiments, that muons when circulating at high velocity, had their lifetime increased, J. Bailey thought that this could be explained by Einstein SR time dilation [1].

After analyzing the proclaimed validation of Einstein SR time dilation by these experiments, we will show that the observed enhanced muon lifetime can be due to the dynamic electrostatic field, necessary to contain the bunch of muons into its trajectory. A way to discriminate between these two explanations is given in conclusion.

2 Experimentation

We will not go into the details of the "muon (g-2) anomaly", which is not due to a possible relativistic effect. Let us say that the purpose is to measure the precession of muons between the frequency of rotation of their circular trajectory and the frequency of rotation of its spin.

The measurement of the "muon (g-2) anomaly" has a long history and started with simpler experiments [2]. In the first experiment (1960 experiment at the CERN facility), muons have a trajectory in the shape of a solenoid and move longitudinally on a distance of 6 m. This device allows muons to make 2000 turns during their travel along the 6 m (corresponding to 2.5 km) and to have a time of storage from 2 to 8 μ s, not sufficient to have a higher precision.

In the second series of experiments at CERN (in 1962-1968), the first done with muons stored in a circular ring, with a radius of 2 m, was realized by injecting muons in a circular ring, after being accelerated at a velocity corresponding to $\gamma = 12$.

The authors asserted that the average lifetime of muons stored in the circular ring was increased to a value of 27 μ s (fig. 8 of the document). But, this value is deduced from the temporal loss of the number of detected positrons (in the case of muons+) or electrons (in the case of muons-) coming from the muons+

or muons- disintegration. It must be understood that there is no direct measurement of the curve of the muons number with time and to assert that this is it, needs a way to discriminate between muons and positron or electron.

The fig. 8 of the reference gives the electron decay for two time scale:

- at short time scale: half of the initial number is attained around $3\mu s$, which shows that the loss of the number of electrons is correlated with the $2.2\mu s$ life time of muons at rest,
- at later time scale: this curve of the electron decay in time scale is far longer and allows the author to say that the muons life time is about $27\mu s$. Also the curve is oscillating while decreasing.

A different interpretation of the later curve could be explained by hypothesizing that the muons bunch disintegrate during the first ten microseconds when entering the ring, with the classical decay law at rest, and turns into a positron or electron bunch instead.

In the third experiment, the second storage ring experiment at the CERN (1969-1976), the muons were injected with a higher energy (higher speed) which would increase the muons lifetime. The fig. 9 of the same document, giving the counting rate versus time, shows the rate is going to zero at around $20\mu s$! Then, in the fig. 11 the decay electron counts versus longer time scale shows a spectacular enhancement of the supposed lifetime of the muons. But again, to say that, you have to be sure that there is still muons in the storage ring. Since there are no other way than counting the electric charges, and that it could be only electrons circulating in the ring.

Nevertheless, there is a way to discriminate between muon and positron or electron. When a muon decay into a positron, the positron emitted is in the direction of the muon spin and more importantly the exponential decay from muon lifetime is modulated by the anomalous precession frequency given by:

$$\omega = \frac{g-2}{2} \frac{e}{m_\mu} B \quad (1)$$

Since the mass of the electron or the positron are far lower than the muon (200 times lower), then it is the way to discriminate between light electric charges and real heavy muons. It can be concluded from this formula and the experimental curve that the muon lifetime is correctly measured by the loss of positron or electron in these experiments.

This increase is proportional to the muons velocity and J.M. Farley tried to demonstrate that the muon lifetime was proportional to the Lorentz factor. This demonstration was discussed by Young-Sea Huang (YSH)[3]. He mentioned that the Lorentz factor value γ is extremely sensitive to the increasing velocity when approaching the speed of light. Since it is difficult to have a precise measurement at which velocity and on which trajectory the muons are moving, then relating the enhancement of the muons lifetime to it is questionable. Also YSH mentioned that J.M. Farley uses a circular reasoning to obtain this value: he makes the hypothesis that Einstein relativity theory is valid to deduce a parameter he is using and after that to obtain the value of $\gamma = 29,327!$

In the following, we propose a reasonable explanation of why the muons lifetime is proportional to the Lorentz factor, more a physical explanation rather than the mathematical Einstein SR formula.

3 New explanation of the muon lifetime

In the muon (g-2) facility, muons are born from pion decay, either positive or negative [4]. In the positive case we have:

$$\pi^+ + (\text{pion}) \rightarrow \mu^+ + (\nu, \mu)(\text{antineutrino}) \quad (2)$$

The negative pion decay gives an electron and a neutrino.

Muon has an electric charge which could be +1 or -1 depending on the electric charge of the pion π decay source. Like the electron or the positron the muon electric charge is without quarks structure [5].

This lack of quark structure could be explained by the presence, inside a true neutral heavy particle, of either a positron or an electron, as it can be the case for protons [6]. When disintegration occurs, the light electric particle is ejected. Probably the antineutrino is there to ensure stability and is also ejected.

The decay of a muon produce either a positron or an electron depending on its electric charge. In the positive case we have:

The lifetime of the muon at rest is measuring the time difference between its stopping and its decay in an electron or a positron and neutrinos. Muons have the peculiarity to have an average lifetime of $2,2 \mu s$ measured at rest

To ensure that the bunch of muons will be kept on a planetary trajectory, magnetic and electrostatic fields are combined. Four electrostatic quadrupoles, covering 43% of the ring, are used to imprint harmonic potential around the central position of the muons beam trajectory [7].

It is known since the 19th century, by Heaviside, that the electrostatic field, received by an electric charge, and emitted by a moving electric charge with constant velocity, is proportional to the Lorentz factor γ [8] [9]. It has been also shown by Jefimenko that this relation is not a mathematical artefact but a real physical effect due to the relative velocity between two electric charges. In the case of the muons moving at constant speed in the circular ring the situation is the reverse since the emitter is at rest and the receiver is moving at constant velocity.

From Heaviside formula it can be seen that when the velocity is close to the speed of light, the electrostatic field is like a “flash” [10], almost perpendicular to the trajectory, and with the amplitude given by:

$$E_\perp = \frac{\int q_i}{4\pi\epsilon_0 d^2} \gamma \quad (4)$$

With $\int q_i$ the sum of the closest electric charges of the quadrupoles acting on the moving muon, ϵ_0 the vacuum permittivity, d the distance between the quadrupoles electric charges and the moving muon, the Lorentz factor $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$, v the muon bunch velocity. The question now is to see if this dynamic electrostatic field can have an effect on the lifetime of the muon.

It has been mentioned by Howard Andrew Ladman [11] that the lifetime of unstable particles could be altered by changing its energy. This author called it Quantum Time Dilation (QTD). He mentioned: “In particular, both of us predict that muon lifetime will be altered by an electrostatic potential to the extent of about 1% per 1.05 MV”. As he said “it is sufficiently outside the mainstream of current physics research that it could be difficult to obtain funding from the usual sources to test it...”!

Moreover, it has been shown by S. Moulih et al, 2020 [12] that the decay of an unstable pion can be largely enhanced by electromagnetic interaction. It was done with a laser with an intensity of the electric field up to 10^8 V/m and a frequency between 0.117 eV and 1.17 eV. Then the pion lifetime at rest, which is $\approx 10^{-8}$ s, can go up to 10^{-5} s, which is a factor 1000 of lifetime dilation!

The authors showed that there is a threshold of the electrostatic field under which there is no enhancement of the lifetime of the pions. This threshold is 10^5 V/m (see fig. 3 and 4 of S. Moulih et al). In contrast, the muon lifetime at rest is $\approx 2.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s, and the observed time dilation in the muon (g-2) experiment has gone up to $\approx 64 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s. The enhancement of lifetime dilation in this case of the muons is only about a factor 30.

The electric field present inside the quadrupoles to maintain the muon bunch on the circular ring is not given in the literature, but only the voltage between the plates of the quadrupoles, which is $18 \cdot 10^3$ V [13] or $25.3 \cdot 10^3$ V [14] at CERN or later at Fermilab. The plates distance being approximatively 4 cm (see Flavour Workshop), the electrostatic field should be about $4 \cdot 10^5$ V/m and $6 \cdot 10^5$ V/m on the muon bunch. These values being above the threshold obtained for pions it is coherent to think these values are also above the threshold for the muon lifetime enhancement by the dynamic electrostatic field.

We have to have in mind that the dynamic electrostatic field is also enhanced by the Lorentz factor due to the muon bunch relative velocity with the static quadrupoles. Then, when the muon bunch velocity is varying, it should vary with this Lorentz factor, and similarly the muon lifetime.

In addition, it has been reported a rapid loss of the positron or electron emitted by the muon decay in the first $10\ \mu\text{s}$ [15] (fig.19). No explanations can come from Einstein SR theory. With our hypothesis, it could be due to two facts. When entering the circular ring, the muons beam is not subjected yet to the quadrupoles and the quadrupoles are covering only 43 % of the ring. Then it could take time to alter the muons structure. At the beginning, the muons lifetime being the one at rest, the number of lost positrons or electrons should respect this lifetime behavior and decrease rapidly. After a while, the effect of the electrostatic field of the quadrupoles could become more and more effective and after $10\ \mu\text{s}$, the new lifetime of the muon would be stabilized. This could be the reason of the rapid loss followed by a stabilization on the new law of time decay.

4 Conclusion

The muon (g-2) anomaly experiment, using muons stored in a circular ring at high velocity, shows a non disputable enhancement of the muon lifetime from its value measured at rest.

The experimenters were probably stunned by this result. Since Einstein SR was predicting a time dilation in an inertial reference frame moving with respect to another inertial reference frame at rest, it is logical that they interpreted their result in such a way. They showed, in a mathematical sense, that it was the Lorentz factor which was responsible for the lifetime enhancement. They didn't suspect there could be another explanation, excepted of the high centripetal acceleration which they rejected without proofs.

In contrast, the effect of the dynamic electrostatic field of the quadrupoles, needed to maintain the muon bunch on the circular ring, is a physical explanation which is probably the reason of the enhancement of the muon bunch lifetime. The strange behavior of the rapid loss of positron or electron in the first $10\ \mu\text{s}$, could be a way to discriminate between the validity of this new explanation and the Einstein SR theory.

These new explanations about the physical reason of the lifetime of muons in a circular ring at high velocities should argue to redo and re-examine the muon (g-2) anomaly lifetime experiments. In the past the funding was dedicated to the precision of the muon (g-2) anomaly parameter. Nowadays, a new goal should be to understand the decay of unstable particles in an electromagnetic field. But it will be endangering Einstein SR theory, then it is unlikely that such a funding could be found.

It has not been the first time that scientist's tried to validate Einstein SR time dilation with high velocity muons. The famous experiment done by David H. Frisch and James H. Smith on atmospheric muons in the earth atmosphere, is taught in every good university. But, it has been shown that there is no time dilation of these unstable high velocity muons. Their penetration in the Earth atmosphere, down to the ground, can be explained with the physical properties of the muons and the Earth atmosphere, even confirmed by their own experimental data [16]!

References

- [1] Measurement of relativistic time dilatation for positive and negative muons on a circular orbit. J Bailey et al. Nature Vol 268, 28 July 1977.
- [2] Muon g-2 and Tests of Relativity. Francis J. M. Farley Energy and Climate Change Division, Engineering and the Environment, Southampton University, Highfield, Southampton, SO17 1BJ, England.

- [3] A Comment on "The Tests of Relativistic Time Dilation in the CERN Muon Storage Ring". Young-Sea Huang. Physics Essays, volume 9, number 2, 1996.
- [4] Measurements of relativistic time dilatation for positive and negative muons in a circular orbit. J. Bailey et al. Nature Vol 268, 28 July 1977.
- [5] <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Muon>.
- [6] Proton and Neutron Electric Charges. Didier Viel. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7623966.
- [7] Measurement of the g-2 of the muon. René Reimann, Flavour Physics Workshop, Neckarzimmern, april 6-8 2022.
- [8] Direct calculation of the electric and magnetic fields of an electric point charge moving with constant velocity. Oleg D. Jefimenko. American Journal of Physics 62, 79-85 (1994). <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.17716>
- [9] Electric Charge Radiation. Didier F. Viel. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10563107
- [10] Dynamic electric field maps of point charge moving with constant velocity. Oleg D. Jefimenko. The Physics Teacher 38, 154 (2000). DOI: 10.1119/1.880481.
- [11] Suitability of the Teachspin Muon Lifetime Device for Testing QTD. Howard Andrew Ladman. [www.researchgate.net/publication, 235420646 SUITABILITY OF THE TEACHSPIN MUON LIFE-TIME DEVICE FOR TESTING QTD](http://www.researchgate.net/publication/235420646_SUITABILITY_OF_THE_TEACHSPIN_MUON_LIFE-TIME_DEVICE_FOR_TESTING_QTD).
- [12] Laser-Assisted Pion Decay. S. Mouslih , M. Jakha , S. Taj and B. Manaut Université Sultan Moulay Slimane, Faculté Polydisciplinaire, Équipe de Recherche en Physique Théorique et Matériaux (ERPTM), Béni Mellal, 23000, Morocco, and E. Siher Faculté des Sciences et Techniques, Laboratoire de Physique des Matériaux (LPM), Béni Mellal, 23000, Morocco. (Dated: October 28, 2020)
- [13] Measurement of the g-2 of the muon. René Reimann, Flavour Physics Workshop, Neckarzimmern, april 6-8 2022.
- [14] The Brookhaven muon (g-2) storage ring high voltage quadrupoles. Yannis K. Semertzidis^{a,*}, Gerald Bennett^b, Efstratios Efstathiadis^a, Frank Krienen^a, Richard Larsen^b, Y.Y. Leeb^c, William M. Morse^b, Yuri Orlov^c, Cenap S. Ozben^b, B. Lee Roberts^a, Louis P. Snyder^b, David S. Warburton^b. Elsevier. 10 February 2003.
- [15] Precise Measurement of the Anomalous Magnetic Moment of the Muon. J. BAILEY, W. BARTL, G. VON BOCHMANN, R.C.A. BROWN, F. J. M. FARLEY, M. GIESCH, H. JOSTLEIN, S. VAN DER MEER, E. PICASSO and R. W. WILLIAMS. Il Nuovo Cimento, Vol. 9A, N.4, 21 Gugno 1972.
- [16] Muons atmospheric time dilation experiment. Didier Viel. Academia.